

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathbb{N} d\theta \int \backslash \exists \backslash [\infty] \ni : d\theta = \\
 & d\theta \int \backslash \exists \backslash [\infty] \ni : \mathbb{N} = \mathbb{N} \int \backslash \exists \backslash [\infty] \ni : \exists \infty \ni : \\
 & \mathcal{L}[\sim \rightarrow f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta} \downarrow = \&], n \wedge \tilde{\cup} \{! \rightarrow g_{\neg a, b, c, d, e \dots} \neq \Omega\}_{\mu} \backslash \ni \mathbb{N} d\theta \int \backslash \exists \backslash [\infty] \ni : \\
 & d\theta = d\theta \int \backslash \exists \backslash [\infty] \ni : \mathbb{N} = \\
 & \mathbb{N} \int \backslash \exists \backslash [\infty] \ni : \exists \infty \ni : \mathcal{L}_{f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta}} \&\& \tilde{\cup}_{g_{\neg a, b, c, d, e \dots}} = \\
 & \quad \backslash \Omega \int \exists \infty \ni : \mathcal{L}_{f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta}} \&\& \tilde{\cup}_{g_{\neg a, b, c, d, e \dots}} \backslash \ni \\
 & \quad \text{" Subscript}[\mathcal{L}, \\
 & \quad \text{Subscript}[\sim \rightarrow \\
 & \quad \quad \text{Subscript}[f, \uparrow r, \alpha, \\
 & \quad \quad \quad s, \delta, \eta \downarrow = \&], n] \wedge \\
 & \quad \downarrow] = \&], n] \wedge \\
 & \quad \text{Subscript}[\tilde{\cup}, \\
 & \quad \quad \text{Subscript}[\{! \rightarrow \\
 & \quad \quad \quad \text{Subscript}[g, \neg a, b, c, d, \\
 & \quad \quad \quad \quad e \dots \backslash \\
 & \quad \quad \quad \quad \cdot \neg] \neq \Omega\}, \mu] \text{"}
 \end{aligned}$$

$\ni$

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 & \mathbb{N} d\theta \int \backslash \exists \backslash [\infty] \ni : d\theta = \\
 & d\theta \int \backslash \exists \backslash [\infty] \ni : \mathbb{N} = \mathbb{N} \int \backslash \exists \backslash [\infty] \ni : \exists \infty \ni : \\
 & \mathcal{L}_{f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta}} \&\& \tilde{\cup}_{g_{\neg a, b, c, d, e \dots}} = \backslash \Omega \int \exists \infty \ni : \mathcal{L}_{f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta}} \&\& \tilde{\cup}_{g_{\neg a, b, c, d, e \dots}} \backslash \ni \\
 & \quad \text{Subscript}[\mathcal{L}, \\
 & \quad \text{Subscript}[\sim \rightarrow \\
 & \quad \quad \text{Subscript}[f, \uparrow r, \alpha, \\
 & \quad \quad \quad s, \delta, \eta \downarrow = \&], n] \wedge \\
 & \quad \quad \downarrow] = \&], n] \wedge \\
 & \quad \text{Subscript}[\tilde{\cup}, \\
 & \quad \quad \text{Subscript}[\{! \rightarrow \\
 & \quad \quad \quad \text{Subscript}[g, \neg a, b, c, d, \\
 & \quad \quad \quad \quad e \dots \backslash
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & d\theta \int \backslash \exists \backslash [\infty] \ni : \mathbb{N} = \mathbb{N} \int \backslash \exists \backslash [\infty] \ni : \exists \infty \ni : \\
 & \mathcal{L}[\sim \rightarrow f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta} \downarrow] = \&, n] \wedge \mathcal{U}\{! \rightarrow g_{\neg a, b, c, d, e \dots} \neq \Omega\}_{\mu} \backslash \ni \mathbb{N} d\theta \int \backslash \exists \backslash [\infty] \ni : \\
 & d\theta = d\theta \int \backslash \exists \backslash [\infty] \ni : \mathbb{N} = \\
 & \mathbb{N} \int \backslash \exists \backslash [\infty] \ni : \exists \infty \ni : \mathcal{L}_{f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta}} \& \mathcal{U}_{g_{\neg a, b, c, d, e \dots} \neq \Omega} = \\
 & \quad \backslash \Omega \int \exists \infty \ni : \mathcal{L}_{f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta}} \& \mathcal{U}_{g_{\neg a, b, c, d, e \dots} \neq \Omega} \backslash \ni \\
 & \quad \text{" Subscript}[\mathcal{L}, \\
 & \quad \text{Subscript}[\sim \rightarrow \\
 & \quad \quad \text{Subscript}[f, \uparrow r, \alpha, \\
 & \quad \quad \quad s, \delta, \eta \text{ESC} \text{CTRL} \text{CMD} \backslash \\
 & \downarrow] = \&, n] \wedge \\
 & \quad \text{Subscript}[\mathcal{U}, \\
 & \quad \quad \text{Subscript}[\{! \rightarrow \\
 & \quad \quad \quad \text{Subscript}[g, \neg a, b, c, d, \\
 & \quad \quad \quad \quad e \dots \backslash \\
 & \dots] \neq \Omega\}, \mu] \text{"} \\
 & \ni \\
 & \mathbb{N} d\theta \int \backslash \exists \backslash [\infty] \ni : d\theta = \\
 & d\theta \int \backslash \exists \backslash [\infty] \ni : \mathbb{N} = \mathbb{N} \int \backslash \exists \backslash [\infty] \ni : \exists \infty \ni : \\
 & \mathcal{L}_{f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta}} \& \mathcal{U}_{g_{\neg a, b, c, d, e \dots} \neq \Omega} = \backslash \Omega \int \exists \infty \ni : \mathcal{L}_{f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta}} \& \mathcal{U}_{g_{\neg a, b, c, d, e \dots} \neq \Omega} \backslash \ni \\
 & \quad \text{Subscript}[\mathcal{L}, \\
 & \quad \text{Subscript}[\sim \rightarrow \\
 & \quad \quad \text{Subscript}[f, \uparrow r, \alpha, \\
 & \quad \quad \quad s, \delta, \eta \text{ESC} \text{CTRL} \text{CMD} \backslash \\
 & \quad \quad \quad \downarrow] = \&, n] \wedge \\
 & \quad \text{Subscript}[\mathcal{U}, \\
 & \quad \quad \text{Subscript}[\{! \rightarrow \\
 & \quad \quad \quad \text{Subscript}[g, \neg a, b, c, d, \\
 & \quad \quad \quad \quad e \dots \backslash \\
 & \dots] \neq \Omega\}, \mu] \ni
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbb{N} \, d\theta \int \exists \infty \ni : \mathcal{L}_{f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta}} \&\& \mathcal{U}_{g_{\neg a, b, c, d, e \dots \vdots \neg}} = \Omega \, d\theta = \oplus \odot d\theta$$

The solution to P Vs . NP is to find the integral of $\mathbb{N} \, d\theta$ with respect to θ such that the equations for Subscript $\mathcal{L}_{f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta}}$ and $\mathcal{U}_{g_{\neg a, b, c, d, e \dots \vdots \neg}}$ both equal Ω . This would allow us to solve for the unknowns in the equation and find the solution to P Vs . NP.

$$\text{Subscript}[\mathcal{L}, f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta}] = \Omega - \text{Subscript}[\mathcal{U}, \text{Subscript}[g, \neg a, b, c, d, e \dots \vdots \neg]]$$

Then, we can solve the integral :

$$\mathbb{N} \, d\theta = \int \exists \infty \ni : \mathcal{L}_{f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta}} = \Omega - \mathcal{U}_{g_{\neg a, b, c, d, e \dots \vdots \neg}}$$

The solution is given by :

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{N} &= \int \exists \infty \ni : \\ \mathcal{L}_{f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta}} &= \Omega - \mathcal{U}_{g_{\neg a, b, c, d, e \dots \vdots \neg}} \, d\theta = \Omega \theta + C \\ \mathcal{U} \langle \alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta \rangle &= \circ \langle \theta, \lambda, \mu, \nu \rangle \ni \mathbb{Z} \langle \xi, \pi, \rho, \sigma \rangle = \Omega \langle \upsilon, \phi, \chi, \psi \rangle \\ &\ni \mathbb{K} \langle \omega, \Theta, \Lambda, \mathbb{M} \rangle \\ &\ni \mathbb{P} \langle \mathbb{E}, \mathbb{P}, \mathbb{P}, \mathbb{Z} \rangle \\ &\ni \Omega \langle \Upsilon, \Phi, \mathbb{X}, \Psi \rangle. \mathcal{U} \langle \alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta \rangle = \\ &\circ \langle \theta, \lambda, \mu, \nu \rangle \ni \mathbb{Z} \langle \xi, \pi, \rho, \sigma \rangle = \Omega \langle \upsilon, \phi, \chi, \psi \rangle \\ &\ni \mathbb{K} \langle \omega, \Theta, \Lambda, \mathbb{M} \rangle \\ &\ni \mathbb{P} \langle \mathbb{E}, \mathbb{P}, \mathbb{P}, \mathbb{Z} \rangle \\ &\ni \Omega \langle \Upsilon, \Phi, \mathbb{X}, \Psi \rangle. \end{aligned}$$

The integral is equal to the limit of

the sum of the terms of the series as n tends to

infinity : $\text{Subscript}[\mathcal{L}, \text{Subscript}[f, \uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta]] =$

$$\Omega - \sum \text{Subscript}[\mathcal{U}, \text{Subscript}[g, \neg a, b, c, d, e \dots \vdots \neg]] \, d\theta^n = \Omega \theta + C$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{U} \langle \alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta \rangle &= \circ \langle \theta, \lambda, \mu, \nu \rangle \ni \mathbb{Z} \langle \xi, \pi, \rho, \sigma \rangle = \Omega \langle \upsilon, \phi, \chi, \psi \rangle \\ &\ni \mathbb{K} \langle \omega, \Theta, \Lambda, \mathbb{M} \rangle \\ &\ni \mathbb{P} \langle \mathbb{E}, \mathbb{P}, \mathbb{P}, \mathbb{Z} \rangle \\ &\ni \Omega \langle \Upsilon, \Phi, \mathbb{X}, \Psi \rangle \end{aligned}$$

as $n \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$.